

LB, 1% PB incidence at harvest results in approximately 0.3% yield loss.

The magnitude of losses caused by PB is close to losses reported for other cultivars in field plot experiments in

Thailand and India. The modified single hill technique allows a preliminary estimate of yield loss in situations where it may be difficult to experiment with many blast severities. □

2. Response surface showing the relationship between yield loss (%), leaf blast (scale of 0-7), and panicle blast (% incidence, PBI) on IR50.

A new sheath rot (ShR) disease of rice identified in Tamil Nadu

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At the end of dry season 1990 (Apr-May), an unidentified ShR disease was observed on rice cultivars IR20 and TKM9 growing on experimental plots in Killikulam. Nearly 7% of rice plants at the boot leaf stage showed disease symptoms, mostly on the sheath enclosing the young panicle. Irregular, dark brown lesions covered much of the sheath. Panicles emerging from diseased plants were mostly black.

The pathogen was identified as *Curvularia lunata* (Walker) Boedijn (IMI

NO. 343370). To test pathogenicity on IR20, a single-grain 15-d-old culture was inserted between the flag leaf sheath and unemerged panicle at the boot leaf stage. The fungus produced characteristic ShR symptoms within 15 d. Symptoms on inoculated plants were similar to those on naturally infected plants.

Infectivity of the fungus was tested on other rice cultivars. A single-grain culture was inserted at the boot leaf stage. Test cultivars were transplanted at 2 seedlings/earthenware pot in insect-proof cages. Five replications of 10 seedlings each were used. Disease severity was scored 15 d after inoculation using a 0-9 scale: 0 = no disease, 1 = less than 1% sheath area affected, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, and 9 = 51-100% sheath area affected. ADT36, ADT38, IR50, ASD7, ASD8, and ASD17 were completely free of disease (see table).

Infectivity of *Curvularia lunata* on Tamil Nadu rice cultivars.

Cultivar	Damage score (0-9)
ADT36	0.0
ADT38	0.0
IR50	0.0
Co 37	5.6
MDU2	3.8
MDU3	5.7
ASD1	7.8
ASD2	9.0
ASD3	1.9
ASD4	2.8
ASD5	2.5
ASD6	4.8
ASD7	0.0
ASD8	0.0
ASD9	3.5
ASD10	5.4
ASD11	3.8
ASD12	7.5
ASD13	8.6
ASD14	3.0
ASD15	7.0
ASD16	5.5
ASD17	0.0
IR20 (check)	9.0
TKM6 (check)	9.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.7

The result was confirmed by a repeated experiment.

Several species of *Curvularia* are known to infect the rice grain, and may even cause leaf spots and seedling blight under certain conditions. But ShR due to *Curvularia lunata* had not been reported previously. □

Effect of asynchronized rice planting on vector abundance and tungro (RTD) infection

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Variation across fields in time of planting the rice crop lengthens the period for an increase in insect pests and diseases and shortens the fallow period during which the numbers of many pest species decline. Insect-transmitted diseases such as RTD are expected to be more prevalent in asynchronously planted areas, because their vectors are

more abundant and because the likelihood is greater that an insect will become a carrier when infected plants are present longer.

In the 1981 wet season, RTD broke out in an irrigated, double-cropped area of Nueva Ecija, Philippines, where we were studying the relationship between insect pest distribution and asynchronizing planting. We selected 14 sites at regular intervals along two transects paralleling irrigation flows.

Using maps and data provided by the irrigation authority, we calculated the planting asynchrony around each site as the standard deviation of planting date (transformed to a cardinal value) in all fields within defined radii (0.2-2.0 km). Insect abundance was measured as total catch over the season in two simple kerosene light traps installed at each site.

We estimated the prevalence of RTD at six sites as the mean infection rate in five fields (150 hills/field) randomly selected within the rotational area (30-ha irrigation management unit) containing the light traps. Diagnosis was based

1. RTD infection at 6 sites in relation to the asynchrony of planting within 0.6 km, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1981 wet season. The best-fitting equation is $Y = -9.12 + 1.28 X$, where Y is arcsin-transformed.

2. RTD infection at 6 sites in relation to the seasonal abundance of GLH. ○ = 1981 wet season; ● = 1982 dry season. The best-fitting equation is $Y = -24.26 + 4.44 X$, where Y is arcsin-transformed.

on visual symptoms and confirmed by starch-iodine test.

RTD prevalence increased with asynchrony of planting within 0.6 km of the sites (maximum correlation $r = 0.83$, $P < 0.05$) (Fig. 1). The abundances of green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix* spp. and of the most efficient vector *N. virescens* were also maximally correlated ($P < 0.05$) with asynchrony within 0.6 km (Fig. 2). This suggests that the mean net displacement of these species over a season is limited.

Other parameters (mean varietal maturity, area devoted to rice, intensity of insecticide use) failed to account for significant additional variation in either disease prevalence or insect abundance.

RTD recurred the following dry season, but estimates of asynchronizing planting were not available. However, taking both seasons together, disease prevalence was significantly correlated with the abundance of both GLH ($r = 0.69$, $P < 0.02$; Fig. 2) and *N. virescens* ($r = 0.61$, $P < 0.05$). □

Field evaluation to control "red stripe," a new rice disease in Vietnam

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"Red stripe" was recorded for the first time in the Mekong Delta in 1988 dry season. The disease developed rapidly in the summer and autumn of 1990. Severe attack caused up to 50% yield loss, due to premature senescence and high ratios of unfilled grain.

We tested the effects of some pesticides on red stripe at disease CLRRI experimental fields. The rice cultivar used was OM59-7. Plot size was 5 × 4 m, 20- × 10-cm plant spacing, in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fertilizer was applied at 100-60-00 kg NPK/ha. All fungicides except one were applied twice, 7 d before

Table 1. Fungicides effective against rice red stripe disease.^a CLRRI, Omon, Haugiang, summer-autumn 1990.

Chemical	Dosage (parts/thousand)	Time of application	Disease severity		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
			% leaves with disease at 7 DAS	% leaf area covered by disease at 14 DAS		
Copper-benlate mixture	2	7 DBH	28.66	12.05	34.9	2.7
Benlate 50 % WP	3	7 DBH	19.86	2.44	36.6	2.4
Triphenyltin-acetate 60 % WP	3	7 DBH	35.84	13.69	36.1	2.4
Oryzemat 8 % G + carbendazim 6 % WP	4 kg ai/ha 2	20 DBH-7 DBH	18.75	0.01	38.5	2.2
Control (unsprayed)	-	-	46.95	52.99	45.1	2.0
LSD (0.01)			15.21	10.86		
(0.05)					6.4	ns

^aDAS = days after spraying, DBH = days before heading.

heading (DBH) and 7 d after heading, using a knapsack sprayer (vol 500 liters/ha). Oryzemat 8% G was applied once at 20 DBH.

Disease severity was measured 7 and 14 d after the second spraying. When disease levels were low, leaves with symptoms were counted in 50-leaf samples. When disease levels were high,

the percentage leaf area covered by disease lesions was measured. Fifty samples were taken in each plot.

Carbendazim, benlate, copper-benlate mixture, and triphenyltin acetate were effective against red stripe disease (Table 1). Kasuran and Oryzemat had no effect (Table 2). □